

John Innes Centre

Unlocking Nature's Diversity

CoARA Action Plan (2026–2031)

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1. Introduction & Institutional Vision

The John Innes Centre (JIC) is a BBSRC-supported Research Institute specialising in plant and microbial science. We are committed to high-quality research conducted with integrity, transparency, and a positive research culture where all staff and students can thrive in a psychologically safe environment.

JIC's Research Culture vision is to create an inclusive, supportive, and fair environment where everyone belongs, feels respected and able to thrive. We embrace team science, prioritise psychological safety and recognise that scientific excellence depends on diversity and collaboration. As a national capability, we will train the next generation, equipping them with the skills and opportunities to contribute to and benefit the wider bioscience ecosystem.

JIC has long been a pioneer in research assessment reform, having been a signatory of the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) since its inception. In 2025, we signed the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) and joined the UK National Chapter to further refine how we evaluate research and recognise diverse outputs.

2. Governance & Oversight

To ensure these commitments are embedded throughout the institute, we have established a clear reporting hierarchy:

CoARA Lead: Head of Science Coordination and Research Culture in the Directorate leadership team attends CoARA meetings including the UK National Chapter and reports back to JIC. The CoARA Lead has responsibility for signing the commitment, drafting the action plan and ensuring it is co-created and communicated.

CoARA Action Working Group: Chaired by the CoARA lead with representation including a Head of Department, Group Leader, and representatives from student, Post-Doc, and Research and Support Staff.

Responsible Research Conduct Committee (RRCC): The Responsible Research Conduct Committee (RRCC) serves as the primary committee contributing to work surrounding institutional integrity and open science. Meeting every four months, the committee brings together representatives from all "voices" across the institute. Additional working groups for specialist topics are set up to feed into this committee. The central purpose of the RRCC is to determine internal policy and champion best practice standards, fostering an environment where research integrity is viewed as a positive and integral component of scientific excellence. Reporting directly to the JIC Research Committee, the RRCC provides strategic advice on the policies and procedures required to underpin responsible research.

The committee's specific functions include:

- **Policy Compliance:** Monitoring and recommending actions to ensure ongoing alignment with the *Concordat to Support Research Integrity* and UKRI *Trusted Research and Innovation* guidance.

- **Culture & Training:** Actively promoting a culture of excellence with integrity by identifying training needs for staff and students and advising on the most effective ways to communicate research guidelines.
- **Operational Oversight:** Managing the biannual pre-publication review process. This initiative promotes best practice in data handling and encourages the involvement of research group members, allowing them to gain direct experience with rigorous methods throughout the process.
- **Problem Solving:** Identifying and addressing the practical barriers or challenges researchers face in complying with integrity obligations to suggest continuous improvements.
- **Support & Confidentiality:** Acting as a trusted resource for both internal staff and external parties. The committee manages concerns regarding research conduct in strict confidence, providing a supportive pathway for individuals to raise issues and ensuring appropriate processes are followed.

JIC Research Committee: The RRCC feeds into the Research Committee to ensure institutional-level embedding of policy and initiatives.

3. Current initiatives

We build this plan on a solid foundation of existing activities:

Inclusivity and Diversity

JIC is committed to a wide range of initiatives around Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI). As Athena Swan Gold holder (renewed in 2023) we have many initiatives supporting gender equality. As a founding signatory of the Technician Commitment (2017), JIC has implemented three action plans to increase the visibility, recognition, career progression and sustainability of technical roles. In this, we actively follow the MI TALENT recommendations to ensure technical staff have opportunities to engage with the wider community. All our staff and students are represented by a 'voice' committee, and these groups have representation on key committees and two-way communication with management.

Pre-publication review

The JIC pre-publication review process is designed to promote excellence in data management and presentation by establishing a culture of best practice among its researchers. By focusing on data integrity, the review ensures that submissions align with institutional standards before they reach the public domain. The process is intentionally 100% advisory, meaning its primary goal is to support and improve the work rather than to delay or prevent publication, thereby encouraging researchers to engage with high-quality data standards in a non-punitive environment.

The initiative fosters open research and transparency by encouraging Group Leaders (GLs) to submit manuscripts that are already available on preprint servers such as BioRxiv. This allows for constructive feedback on work that is already publicly accessible but not yet finalised in a journal, bridging the gap between rapid dissemination and formal peer review. The process is not intended to review every manuscript produced at JIC, but rather to ensure that each research group periodically has at least one manuscript reviewed. Through a rotating schedule in which groups either review or are reviewed every couple of years, the process provides broad institutional coverage while remaining proportionate and manageable. This

approach ensures that good practice is shared across all groups without creating unnecessary burden.

Finally, the review serves as a vital training and collegiate development tool. While GLs carry ultimate responsibility for engagement, the participation of first or corresponding authors is encouraged, providing junior researchers with hands-on experience in high-level data review and best practice. By selecting reviewers with relevant subject expertise to provide constructive feedback, the institute fosters a peer-to-peer learning environment that strengthens the professional skills of both reviewers and authors. To date, 29 reviews have been completed since 2022.

Ethics training

An ethics workshop has been run annually for many years and is an opportunity to hear expert and first-hand advice and information on ethical infractions in scientific publishing: including plagiarism, duplicate publication, authorship, image manipulation, data fabrication and falsification, challenging the system, corrections, retractions and the costs of malpractice. This is compulsory for all students to complete in their first year and all staff are encouraged to attend.

Open Access

The [UKRI Open Access policy](#) applies to in-scope outputs published by UKRI or BBSRC-funded authors, and all JIC staff are encouraged to make their publications open access and comply with the policy. The institute has Jisc-negotiated transformative agreements with publishers that cover 91% of journal article output, and staff are also encouraged to make long-form publications open access via the UKRI's open access fund for monographs.

Financial Year	2022/2023	2023/2024	2024/2025	2025/2026
JIC Research articles				
Total/Gold/Green	102/5/120	93/5/107	66/2/71	32/1/36
% UKRI compliance	89%	92%	96%	92%

JIC Research Integrity Panel

The JIC Research Integrity Panel is made up of experienced staff members from across the institute. The panel provide confidential advice and support to all JIC researchers relating to matters of scientific integrity, research best practice and issues relating to the publication of results. The panel are very willing and able to answer questions and address concerns in these areas, and all conversations are treated in strict confidence.

4. JIC CoARA action plan – 2026-2031

Core Commitments			
Action(s)	Responsibility	Timescale	Measure of success
1	Recognise the diversity of contributions: Value the various roles, outputs, and career paths in research (e.g., datasets, software, policy contributions) rather than just journal publications.		
Narrative CVs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure Resume for Researcher and Innovation (R4RI) is used in institute submissions to BBSRC and for grant proposals when appropriate. Ensure these recognise diverse talents and competencies. 	All, Peer Review Panel	2026-2031	A set of narrative CVs that can be used as examples to support others.
Technician Commitment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue to Deliver our Technician Commitment Action Plan to valuing technical and professional contributions. Self-assessment of the 2023-2026 action plan and new action plan prepared for 2027-2030 	Technician Commitment working group Technician Commitment working group	2026-2031 2027	Collect impact to evidence this Submit assessment and action plan in 2027
Professional Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review promotion criteria and how they are assessed especially for non-Group Leader roles. 	People and Culture Committee	2027	Reviewed documentation for non-GL roles

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review different career paths and look at a variety of options for professional development and recognition. Review how we put people forward for recognition awards to ensure we value diversity of contributions 	People and Culture Committee	2026-2031	Examples of where alternative routes exist and have been communicated
	Directorate/Research Committee	2026-2031(?)	Paper presented for Research Committee (2026) and record of awards submitted centrally
<p>Tenure Track</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement the Tenure Track Framework giving support to ensure mentoring is provided effectively and assessment follows CoARA principles. 	Directorate/ApCom	2026	New Tenure Track Framework support shared with all current staff and new recruits
<p>Fair Attribution Policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish a fair attribution policy based on CRediT Taxonomy. Ensure the use of this is checked in publication audit 	RRCC	2026-2027	Policy available and Infographic shared with all faculty on CRediT taxonomy.
2	Focus on qualitative evaluation: Base assessments primarily on qualitative judgment where peer review is central, supported by the responsible (rather than dominant) use of quantitative indicators.		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Include quantitative data (funding, citations) with qualitative indicators (case studies, narratives) in research assessment. 	ApCom/Promotion Committee	2026-2031	Responsible quantitative and qualitative evaluation used in Group Leader recruitment and Tenure Track review

3	Abandon inappropriate metrics: Move away from using journal- and publication-based metrics as proxies for quality, specifically the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and the h-index.		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remove H-index information from internal publication database (NBIROS) 	Library & IS	2026	h-index removed
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Audit and ensure JIF and h-index are not used in research assessment processes. 	ApCom/HR	2027	Completion of an audit of HR and recruitment templates to ensure JIF/h-index fields are removed by 2027
4	Avoid organisational rankings: Ensure that the rankings of research organisations do not influence the assessment of individual researchers or their projects.		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prepare infographic to be shared with all science recruitments as reminder to CoARA principles 	Directorate/ApCom	2027	Infographic completed and used in science recruitments

Supporting Commitments			
Action(s)	Responsibility	Timescale	Measure of success
5	Commit resources: Allocate the necessary funding and staff time to achieve the organisational changes required by the reform.		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dedicated roles exist for Research Culture and Responsible Research assessment. Ensure these roles are recognised. Allocate staff time to participate in CoARA working groups and Responsible Research Committee 	Directorate/RRCC	2026-2031	RRCC committee ToRs
	Directorate/RRCC	2026-2031	Evidence of range of staff contributions
6	Review and develop criteria: Continually update research assessment criteria, tools, and processes to align with the core principles.		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review Action plan every 6 months by CoARA working group and table at RRCC annually Review the Tenure Track Framework and recruitment processes to ensure alignment with the core principles 	CoARA Working Group/RRCC	2026-2031	Evidence of updates and minutes of meeting

7	Raise awareness and provide training: Communicate the reforms clearly and provide guidance and training for those involved in assessment.		
<p>Many of the actions highlighted for commitment 1 will support this. Awareness raising and training planned include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infographic prepared on CoARA principles • CRediT Awareness raising through fair attribution policy and other communication routes to provide information on ethical use of CRediT to ensure that researchers and technical staff receive appropriate formal recognition for their specific roles in collaborative projects. • Ethics/Research Integrity training course • Internal comms campaign around JIF, H Index and the importance of CoARA 	<p>Directorate/ApCom</p> <p>RRCC/Directorate</p> <p>Training and Development</p> <p>Directorate/Comms</p>	<p>2026-2027</p> <p>2026-2027</p> <p>2026-2028</p> <p>2026-2031</p>	<p>Infographic available and communicated</p> <p>Policy Published which includes CRediT</p> <p>Ethics course continues to run and broader research integrity incorporated</p> <p>1/year awareness raising of CoARA in newsletter</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include CoARA principles in the Welcome meeting for all staff and students to ensure the next generation understands qualitative assessment from Day 1 	Directorate/Comms	2026-2031	Included in Welcome booklet and meeting
8	Exchange practices: Share experiences and lessons learned with other organisations within the coalition to enable mutual learning.			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actively participating in the CoARA UK National Chapter 	Directorate	2026-2031	Attend meetings/events
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share our CoARA journey with other BBSRC institutes 	Directorate	2026-2031	Share our action plan and experience at the connecting culture meeting
9	Communicate progress: Be transparent about how your organisation is adhering to the principles and implementing the commitments.			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish this action plan on Zenodo and maintain transparent communication of evaluation processes. 	Directorate	2026	Uploaded to Zenodo

10	Evaluate based on evidence: Use research-on-research (meta-research) to evaluate the effectiveness of new assessment tools and make that data openly available.		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include questions around research assessment in the staff survey • Obtain feedback from staff who have been through Tenure Track Framework 	HR	2026	Question around CoARA principles included in staff survey